

Simultaneous Estimation of Frusemide and Spironolactone from their Combined Dosage form by HPTLC

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The combination of frusemide and spironolactone is used in the treatment of mild to moderate essential hypertension. Though literature survey reveals several methods of analysis¹ of these drugs individually or in combination with other drugs, HPTLC method has not been reported so far. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Precoated HPTLC silica gel 60 F_{254} plates (E. Merck) were used for chromatographic separation. Quantification of individual component was carried out using a Camag TLC II densitometer with Cat's 3-14 chromatographic software.

Solutions of standard frusemide (99.46%) and spironolactone (99.36%) of pharmacopoeial specifications were prepared in methanol and mixed in appropriate ratio and diluted with methanol to obtain different concentrations in the range 0.8–2.0 and 2–14 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. The detector response was found to be linear in the above mentioned range.

Procedure : From the finely powdered sample of fixed dose combination containing 20 mg frusemide and 50 mg spironolactone, powder equivalent to 20 mg of frusemide was dissolved and diluted to 50 ml with methanol. The solution was filtered and filtrate was used.

Four microliters of the sample as well as the standard were applied to chromatoplate. Chromatographic development was carried out with mobile phase containing ethyl acetate : n-hexane : glacial acetic acid (60 : 40 : 0.5, by vol.) for 12 min. The plate was then dried in a current of hot air and subjected to densitometric scanning.

Although the λ_{max} for frusemide and spironolactone are 271 and 242 nm respectively, but most suitable wavelength 265 nm was selected without affecting precision and accuracy of the method. Both the compounds were simultaneously detected at this wavelength. From the peak areas of standard and sample, the percentage assay values were calculated (Table 1).

Reproducibility and inter-assay variation were determined by replicate analysis of sample. Lower values of coefficient of variation for individual ingredient indicate the precision of the method. The method free from interference from excipients, is suitable for routine analysis of several similar samples.

TABLE I

Drug	Labelled mg	Found mg	% Assay	COV %
Frusemide	20	19.88	99.4	1.1
Spironolactone	50	51.04	102.1	1.3

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